

RESEARCH PROTOCOL: Effectiveness of Teledentistry and mHealth Interventions Compared to Traditional In-Person Dental Care: An Umbrella Review of Systematic Reviews

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ABSTRACT

Background: Systematic reviews of digital health technologies in dentistry report inconsistent findings. Heterogeneous results and overlapping primary studies necessitate comprehensive evidence synthesis.

Objective: To evaluate teledentistry and mobile health (mHealth) intervention effectiveness compared to traditional dental care for oral health outcomes.

Methods: This umbrella review follows Cochrane methodology and PRIOR guidelines. Five databases (Cochrane Database, MEDLINE, Embase, LILACS, Epistemonikos) will be searched from 2010-2024 for systematic reviews of teledentistry and mHealth interventions. Eligible reviews include RCTs, quasi-RCTs, cohort, or cross-sectional studies comparing digital interventions versus traditional care. Primary outcomes: plaque indices, gingival parameters, dental caries measures. Two reviewers will extract data using metaumbrella-compatible forms. Quality assessment uses AMSTAR-2. Meta-analytic estimates will be recalculated using random-effects models, converting effect sizes to equivalent Hedges' g or odds ratios. Evidence stratification follows Ioannidis criteria. Systematic review overlap will be quantified using corrected covered area calculations. GRADE approach evaluates evidence certainty.

Expected Results: This synthesis will establish robust evidence for digital health intervention effectiveness in dentistry and inform clinical practice guidelines.

Keywords: umbrella review; teledentistry; mobile health; systematic review; evidence synthesis

INTRODUCTION

Digital health technologies have gained prominence in healthcare delivery, with teledentistry and mobile health (mHealth) emerging as promising approaches for oral healthcare provision (Mariño et al., 2024). Teledentistry encompasses the use of telecommunication technologies to deliver dental care, consultation, and education remotely through synchronous (real-time) or asynchronous (store-and-forward) modalities (Mariño et al., 2024). mHealth refers to mobile technologies that facilitate health services and information delivery through mobile devices, applications, and messaging systems (Mariño et al., 2024).

Multiple systematic reviews have evaluated these technologies across various oral health conditions (Al-Buhaisi et al., 2024; Emami et al., 2022; Estai et al., 2018; Fernández et al., 2021; Toniazzo et al., 2019), with findings suggesting potential benefits in access to care, patient education, and clinical outcomes. However, results remain inconsistent across different populations, settings, and outcome measures. Some reviews report significant improvements in plaque control and gingival health through mHealth interventions (Fernández et al., 2021; Murariu et al., 2025), while others show minimal differences compared to traditional care approaches (Murariu et al., 2025). This heterogeneity in findings, combined with varying methodological approaches and overlapping primary studies across reviews, necessitates a comprehensive umbrella review (Fusar-Poli and Radua, 2018; Ioannidis, 2009).

Objectives

Primary Objective: To evaluate the effectiveness of teledentistry and mHealth interventions compared to traditional in-person dental care for improving oral health clinical outcomes.

Secondary Objectives: 1. To assess the certainty of evidence for each intervention-outcome combination using established criteria 2. To quantify the degree of overlap among existing systematic reviews 3. To identify knowledge gaps and future research priorities.

METHODS

Study Design and Registration

This umbrella review will adhere to the Cochrane Handbook for Overviews of Reviews methodology and the PRIOR reporting guideline (Gates et al., 2022). The protocol is reported according to PRISMA-P guidelines (Moher et al., 2015) and will be registered in OSF repository prior to study commencement.

Eligibility Criteria

Types of Studies: Systematic reviews with or without meta-analysis that include primary studies (randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized trials, cohort studies, or cross-sectional studies). Systematic reviews will be defined as evidence syntheses that: (1) aim to answer pre-specified research questions, (2) establish eligibility criteria a priori, (3) employ a search strategy involving at least two databases, and (4) assess risk of bias of included studies. Rapid reviews meeting these criteria will be included.

Population: Individuals of any age requiring oral health care.

Interventions: - Teledentistry interventions (synchronous or asynchronous modalities) - mHealth interventions (mobile applications, SMS/messaging systems, wearable devices)

Comparators: Traditional in-person dental care or usual care.

Outcomes:

Primary outcomes (continuous): - Plaque index/score - Gingival index/bleeding on probing - Dental caries increment (DMFT/dmft)

Primary outcomes (binary): - Presence of dental caries - Gingivitis/periodontitis diagnosis - Treatment completion rates

Secondary outcomes: - Patient satisfaction scores - Knowledge/behavior change measures - Cost-effectiveness indicators

Language: English, German, Spanish, Italian, and Portuguese.

Timeframe: January 2010 to December 2024 (justified by emergence of modern teledentistry/mHealth technologies post-2010).

Search Strategy

Electronic databases will be searched from January 2010 to December 2024: - Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews - MEDLINE (via PubMed) - Embase - LILACS - Epistemonikos

Search Strategy Components:

("teledentistry" OR "tele-dentistry" OR "mobile health" OR "mHealth" OR "mobile application" OR "smartphone" OR "text message" OR "telehealth" OR "digital health")

AND

("oral health" OR "dental" OR "dentistry" OR "periodontal" OR "gingival" OR "caries" OR "plaque")

AND

("systematic review" OR "meta-analysis" OR "overview" OR "umbrella review")

Reference lists of included reviews will be manually screened. McMaster methodological filters will be applied where available.

Study Selection

At least two reviewers will independently screen titles/abstracts using Rayyan platform, followed by full-text screening. Disagreements will be resolved through consensus or third reviewer consultation. Selection will be conducted using Covidence software and documented using PRISMA flow diagram.

Management of Overlapping Systematic Reviews

Overlap Assessment: 1. Visual Matrix: Construction of citation matrix showing primary studies across systematic reviews 2. Quantitative Assessment: Calculation of Corrected Covered Area (CCA) and weighted CCA (wCCA) when sample size data available 3. Interpretation: Overlap classified as slight (0-5%), moderate (6-10%), high (11-15%), or very high (>15%) (Ying et al., 2025) .

Decision Rules for Overlapping Reviews: When multiple systematic reviews address identical intervention-outcome combinations:

1. Select review with largest number of primary studies
2. If equivalent size, select most recent review

3. If published within same year, select review with highest AMSTAR-2 rating (Shea et al., 2017)
4. Document all decisions with rationale

Sensitivity Analyses: - Analysis excluding reviews with very high overlap (>15% CCA) - Analysis limited to highest quality reviews (AMSTAR-2 moderate/high) - Temporal sensitivity analysis (reviews published 2010-2017 vs 2018-2024)

All the analysis for the overlap will be conducted using R package ccaR (Bougioukas et al., 2022).

Data Extraction

Data will be extracted independently by at least two reviewers using a standardized form designed for metaumbrella package compatibility (Gosling et al., 2023). Discrepancies resolved through the intervention of RM.

Data Extraction Form (see details in

Study Identification: - author: First author surname - year: Publication year
- factor: Intervention-outcome combination identifier - population: Study population characteristics

Effect Size Data: - measure: Effect size type (SMD, OR, RR, Hedges_g, etc.) - effect_size: Pooled effect estimate - ci_lo: Lower 95% confidence interval - ci_up: Upper 95% confidence interval
- pi_lo: Lower 95% prediction interval (if available) - pi_up: Upper 95% prediction interval (if available) - p_value: P-value of pooled effect

Study Characteristics: - n_studies: Number of primary studies included - n_participants: Total number of participants - n_cases: Number of cases (for binary outcomes) - n_controls: Number of controls (for binary outcomes)

Heterogeneity and Bias Indicators: - I2: I-squared statistic (%) - egger_p: P-value from Egger's test for small-study effects - esb_p: P-value from excess significance bias test - largest_ci_lo: Lower CI of largest study - largest_ci_up: Upper CI of largest study - jackknife_p: P-value from jackknife analysis

Quality Assessment: - amstar_score: AMSTAR-2 overall rating - amstar_critical_flaws: Number of critical flaws - rob_overall: Overall risk of bias assessment of primary studies

Risk of Bias Assessment

Systematic Reviews: AMSTAR-2 (16-item checklist) applied independently by two reviewers.

Primary Studies: Extract risk of bias assessments as reported in systematic reviews. If systematic reviews used RoB 2.0 (for RCTs) or ROBINS-I (for non-RCTs), extract this information. Otherwise, note assessment method used.

Data Synthesis and Analysis

Statistical Analysis: All analyses conducted using metaumbrella R package (Gosling et al., 2023).

Meta-analytic Procedures: 1. **Recalculation:** Meta-analytic estimates recalculated using random-effects models (DerSimonian-Laird method) 2. **Effect Size Harmonization:** All effect sizes converted to equivalent Hedges' g (continuous outcomes) or equivalent OR (binary outcomes) for comparison 3. **Heterogeneity Assessment:** I^2 statistics and 95% prediction intervals 4. **Small-study Effects:** Egger's test for asymmetry 5. **Excess Significance:** Test for excess statistical significance bias 6. **Robustness:** Jackknife leave-one-out analyses

Evidence Stratification: Evidence will be classified using Ioannidis criteria (Fusar-Poli & Radua, 2018):

- **Class I (Convincing):** $p < 10^{-6}$, >1000 participants, $I^2 < 50\%$, 95% prediction interval excludes null, no small-study effects, no excess significance bias
- **Class II (Highly Suggestive):** $p < 10^{-6}$, >1000 participants, largest study significant, Class I criteria not met

- **Class III (Suggestive):** $p < 10^{-3}$, >1000 participants, Class I-II criteria not met
- **Class IV (Weak):** $p < 0.05$, Class I-III criteria not met
- **Class V (Non-significant):** $p \geq 0.05$

Certainty of Evidence Assessment

GRADE approach will be used to evaluate certainty of evidence, considering: 1) Risk of bias in systematic reviews and primary studies, 2) Inconsistency across studies, 3) Indirectness of evidence, 4) Imprecision of estimates, and 5) Publication bias indicators.

Summary of findings tables will be generated using GRADEpro GDT software¹.

Sensitivity Analyses

1. **Quality-based:** Analysis limited to high/moderate quality systematic reviews (AMSTAR-2)
2. **Study Design:** Analysis limited to systematic reviews including only RCTs
3. **Overlap-based:** Analysis excluding systematic reviews with very high overlap
4. **Temporal:** Comparison of findings from earlier (2010-2017) vs recent (2018-2024) reviews

Data Management and Open Science

Data Sharing: Full protocol, data extraction forms, analysis code, and datasets will be made available through Open Science Framework (OSF) repository under CC-BY 4.0 license.

¹ Log in <https://gdt.grade.pro.org/app/#projects> with RSU account

Software: All analyses will be conducted in R (version 4.3+) using: - metaumbrella package for umbrella review analyses - ccaR package for overlap assessment - GRADEpro GDT for certainty of evidence tables

Ethics and Dissemination

Ethical approval is not required as this study uses only published data. Findings will be disseminated through peer-reviewed publication and conference presentations.

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APPENDIX A: Complete Search Strategies

PubMed Search Strategy

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((("Teledentistry"[Mesh] OR "teledentistry"[tiab] OR "tele-dentistry"[tiab] OR "telehealth"[tiab] OR "teleconsultation"[tiab]) OR ("mobile health"[tiab] OR "mHealth"[tiab] OR "mobile application"[tiab] OR "mobile app"[tiab] OR "smartphone"[tiab] OR "text message"[tiab] OR "SMS"[tiab])) AND ("oral health"[tiab] OR "dental health"[tiab] OR "dentistry"[tiab] OR "periodontal"[tiab] OR "gingival"[tiab] OR "dental caries"[tiab] OR "plaque"[tiab] OR "gingivitis"[tiab] OR "periodontitis"[tiab])) AND (("systematic review"[Publication Type] OR "meta-analysis"[Publication Type] OR "systematic review"[tiab] OR "meta-analysis"[tiab] OR "umbrella review"[tiab] OR "overview of reviews"[tiab]) AND ("2010/01/01"[PDAT] : "2024/12/31"[PDAT]))
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Embase Search Strategy

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('teledentistry'/exp OR 'teledentistry':ti,ab OR 'mobile health'/exp OR 'mHealth':ti,ab OR 'smartphone'/exp OR 'mobile application':ti,ab) AND ('oral health'/exp OR 'dental caries'/exp OR 'periodontal disease'/exp OR 'plaque':ti,ab OR 'gingivitis':ti,ab) AND ('systematic review'/exp OR 'meta analysis'/exp OR 'umbrella review':ti,ab OR 'overview of reviews':ti,ab) AND [2010-2024]/py
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APPENDIX B: Data Extraction Form Template

Data Extraction Form Template: Teledentistry and mHealth Umbrella Review

Instructions for Data Extractors

General Guidelines:

- Extract data independently in duplicate
- Use standardized coding as specified below
- Enter “NR” for Not Reported, “NA” for Not Applicable
- Include exact page numbers for key data points
- When multiple effect sizes reported for same outcome, extract the primary/main analysis
- For missing data, attempt calculation from available information when possible

SECTION A: STUDY IDENTIFICATION AND CHARACTERISTICS

Variable Name	Description	Data Type	Coding Instructions	Example
study_id	Unique study identifier	Text	FirstAuthor_Year_OutcomeCode	Smith_2023_PI
first_author	First author surname	Text	Surname only, no initials	Smith
year	Publication year	Numeric	Four-digit year	2023
journal	Journal name	Text	Full journal name	Journal of Dental Research
doi	Document Object Identifier	Text	Complete DOI without https://	10.1177/00220345231234567
pmid	PubMed ID	Numeric	PMID number only	12345678
prospero_id	PROSPERO registration number	Text	Full registration ID or “NR”	CRD42023123456

country_first_author	Country of first author affiliation	Text	Full country name	United States
language	Publication language	Text	English/Spanish/German/Italian/Portuguese	English
review_type	Type of systematic review	Categorical	1=SR only, 2=SR+MA, 3=Network MA, 4=Other	2

SECTION B: REVIEW CHARACTERISTICS

Variable Name	Description	Data Type	Coding Instructions	Example
objective_primary	Primary objective of review	Text	Copy verbatim from abstract/methods	To evaluate effectiveness of mHealth apps
population_age	Target population age	Categorical	1=Children, 2=Adults, 3=Mixed, 4=Elderly, 5=All ages	3
population_setting	Clinical setting	Categorical	1=Primary care, 2=Hospital, 3=Community, 4=Mixed, 5=NR	4
intervention_type	Type of digital intervention	Categorical	1=Teledentistry sync, 2=Teledentistry async, 3=mHealth app, 4=SMS/messaging, 5=Mixed, 6=Other	3
intervention_description	Detailed intervention description	Text	Copy key components from methods	Mobile app with daily oral hygiene reminders and education

comparator_type	Type of comparator	Categorical	1=In-person care, 2=Usual care, 3=No intervention, 4=Other digital, 5=Mixed	1
oral_condition	Target oral health condition	Categorical	1=Caries, 2=Periodontal, 3=Oral hygiene, 4=Mixed, 5=Other	2
search_databases_n	Number of databases searched	Numeric	Count of unique databases	5
search_date_from	Search date range start	Text	YYYY-MM format or "NR"	
search_date_to	Search date range end	Text	YYYY-MM format	2022-12

SECTION C: OUTCOME-SPECIFIC DATA (metaumbrella core variables)

Variable Name	Description	Data Type	Coding Instructions	Example
factor	Intervention-outcome combination	Text	InterventionType_OutcomeType_Population	mHealth_PlaqueIndex_Adults
outcome_name	Specific outcome measured	Text	Standardized outcome name	Plaque Index
outcome_definition	How outcome was defined/measured	Text	Copy measurement details	Modified Quigley-Hein Plaque Index
outcome_timepoint	Follow-up timepoint	Text	Time from baseline (weeks/months)	12 weeks
measure_value	Effect size estimate	Text	SMD/OR/RR/MD/Hedges_g/Risk difference	SMD -0.45
ci_lo	Lower 95% confidence interval	Numeric	Lower CI boundary	-0.78

ci_up	Upper 95% confidence interval	Numeric	Upper CI boundary	-0.12
p_value	P-value of pooled effect	Numeric	Exact p-value (use < 0.001 if very small)	0.007
pi_lo	Lower 95% prediction interval	Numeric	Lower PI boundary or "NR"	-1.23
pi_up	Upper 95% prediction interval	Numeric	Upper PI boundary or "NR"	0.33

SECTION D: STUDY COMPOSITION AND HETEROGENEITY

Variable Name	Description	Data Type	Coding Instructions	Example
n_studies	Number of included studies	Numeric	Count of primary studies in meta-analysis	8
total_n	Total number of participants	Numeric	Sum across all included studies	1247
n_cases	Number of cases	Numeric	For binary outcomes, total cases	234
n_controls	Number of controls	Numeric	For binary outcomes, total controls	456
study_designs	Types of study designs included	Text	List primary study designs	RCT, Quasi-RCT
I2	I-squared heterogeneity statistic	Numeric	Percentage (0-100)	67
Q_statistic	Cochran's Q statistic	Numeric	Q value or "NR"	23.45
Q_p_value	P-value for Q statistic	Numeric	P-value for heterogeneity test	0.003
tau_squared	Tau-squared value	Numeric	Between-study variance or "NR"	0.12

SECTION E: BIAS ASSESSMENT INDICATORS

Variable Name	Description	Data Type	Coding Instructions	Example
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egger_p	Egger's test p-value	Numeric	P-value for small-study effects or "NR"	0.23
begg_p	Begg's test p-value	Numeric	P-value for rank correlation test or "NR"	0.45
funnel_plot	Funnel plot assessment	Categorical	1=Symmetric, 2=Asymmetric, 3=Unclear, 4=NR	2
trim_fill_studies	Number of studies imputed by trim-fill	Numeric	Count of imputed studies or "NR"	2
largest_study_n	Sample size of largest study	Numeric	N of largest included study	345
largest_study_effect	Effect size of largest study	Numeric	Effect size from largest study	-0.23
largest_ci_lo	Lower CI of largest study	Numeric	Lower CI of largest study effect	-0.67
largest_ci_up	Upper CI of largest study	Numeric	Upper CI of largest study effect	0.21
excess_significance_p	Excess significance test p-value	Numeric	P-value for excess significance bias or "NR"	0.78
jackknife_range_lo	Jackknife analysis lower bound	Numeric	Lowest effect size in leave-one-out	-0.56
jackknife_range_up	Jackknife analysis upper bound	Numeric	Highest effect size in leave-one-out	-0.34

SECTION F: QUALITY ASSESSMENT (AMSTAR-2)

Variable Name	Description	Data Type	Coding Instructions	Example
amstar2_q1	PICO statement	Categorical	1=Yes, 2=Partial Yes, 3=No	1
amstar2_q2	Protocol registration	Categorical	1=Yes, 2=Partial Yes, 3=No	1

amstar2_q3	Study design explanation	Categorical	1=Yes, 2=Partial Yes, 3=No	2
amstar2_q4	Comprehensive search	Categorical	1=Yes, 2=Partial Yes, 3=No	1
amstar2_q5	Duplicate selection	Categorical	1=Yes, 2=Partial Yes, 3=No	1
amstar2_q6	Duplicate extraction	Categorical	1=Yes, 2=Partial Yes, 3=No	1
amstar2_q7	Excluded studies list	Categorical	1=Yes, 2=Partial Yes, 3=No	3
amstar2_q8	Study characteristics	Categorical	1=Yes, 2=Partial Yes, 3=No	1
amstar2_q9	Risk of bias assessment	Categorical	1=Yes, 2=Partial Yes, 3=No	1
amstar2_q10	Funding sources	Categorical	1=Yes, 2=Partial Yes, 3=No	2
amstar2_q11	Meta-analysis methods	Categorical	1=Yes, 2=Partial Yes, 3=No, 4=NA	1
amstar2_q12	Risk of bias consideration	Categorical	1=Yes, 2=Partial Yes, 3=No	1
amstar2_q13	Risk of bias discussion	Categorical	1=Yes, 2=Partial Yes, 3=No	2
amstar2_q14	Heterogeneity explanation	Categorical	1=Yes, 2=Partial Yes, 3=No	1
amstar2_q15	Publication bias investigation	Categorical	1=Yes, 2=Partial Yes, 3=No	2
amstar2_q16	Conflict of interest	Categorical	1=Yes, 2=Partial Yes, 3=No	1
amstar2_overall	Overall AMSTAR-2 rating	Categorical	1=High, 2=Moderate, 3=Low, 4=Critically low	2
amstar2_critical_flaws	Number of critical flaws	Numeric	Count of critical domain failures	1

SECTION G: PRIMARY STUDY RISK OF BIAS (FOR OVERLAPPING)

Variable Name	Description	Data Type	Coding Instructions	Example
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rob_tool_used	Risk of bias tool used in SR	Text	FOR OVERLAPPING - Name of RoB tool	Cochrane RoB 2.0
rob_domains_assessed	Domains assessed	Text	FOR OVERLAPPING - List domains evaluated	Randomization, blinding, attrition
rob_overall_primary	Overall RoB of primary studies	Categorical	FOR OVERLAPPING - 1=Low, 2=Some concerns, 3=High, 4=Mixed	2
rob_percentage_low	Percentage of studies with low RoB	Numeric	FOR OVERLAPPING - Percentage (0-100)	45
primary_study_list	List of included primary studies	Text	FOR OVERLAPPING - FirstAuthor_Year separated by semicolons	Smith_2020;Jones_2021;Brown_2022

SECTION H: OVERLAP ASSESSMENT VARIABLES (FOR OVERLAPPING)

Variable Name	Description	Data Type	Coding Instructions	Example
overlap_factor_code	Standardized factor code for overlap analysis	Text	FOR OVERLAPPING - InterventionCode_Outcome Code	MHEALTH_PLAQUE
overlap_population_code	Population code for overlap	Text	FOR OVERLAPPING - ADULT/CHILD/MIXED/ELDERLY	ADULT

overlap_intervention_detail	Specific intervention for overlap	Text	FOR OVERLAPPING - Detailed intervention type	Mobile app with reminders
overlap_outcome_detail	Specific outcome for overlap	Text	FOR OVERLAPPING - Exact outcome definition	Plaque Index (Quigley-Hein)
overlap_timepoint_months	Follow-up time in months	Numeric	FOR OVERLAPPING - Convert all to months in months	3
overlap_included_studies_detail	Detailed list for overlap	Text	FOR OVERLAPPING - FirstAuthor_Year_StudyDesign_SampleSize	Smith_2020_RCT_120;Jones_2021_RCT_89
overlap_search_enddate	End date of systematic review search	Text	FOR OVERLAPPING - YYYY-MM-DD format	2022-12-31
overlap_geographic_scope	Geographic scope of included studies	Text	FOR OVERLAPPING - Countries/regions included	USA, Canada, UK, Australia

SECTION I: ADDITIONAL METAUMBRELLA VARIABLES

Variable Name	Description	Data Type	Coding Instructions	Example
power_calculation	Statistical power calculation	Numeric	Power to detect SMD=0.5 at $\alpha=0.05$ or "NR"	0.85
sensitivity_analysis	Sensitivity analyses performed	Text	List sensitivity analyses conducted	Risk of bias, study design
subgroup_analysis	Subgroup analyses performed	Text	List subgroup variables analyzed	Age groups, intervention duration

grade_certainty	GRADE certainty assessment	Categorical	1=High, 2=Moderate, 3=Low, 4=Very low, 5=NR	3
clinical_significance	Authors' assessment of clinical significance	Categorical	1=Clinically significant, 2=Not significant, 3=Unclear, 4=NR	1

SECTION J: EXTRACTOR INFORMATION AND QUALITY CONTROL

Variable Name	Description	Data Type	Coding Instructions	Example
extractor_id	Data extractor identifier	Text	Initials of extractor	SEU
extraction_date	Date of data extraction	Text	YYYY-MM-DD format	2024-01-15
page_numbers	Page numbers for key data	Text	Pages where main results found	156, 158-160
extraction_confidence	Confidence in data extraction	Categorical	1=High, 2=Moderate, 3=Low	1
clarification_needed	Items requiring clarification	Text	List any unclear items	Effect size calculation method
extraction_notes	Additional notes	Text	Any relevant observations	Multiple timepoints reported, used longest

CODING REFERENCE SHEET

Intervention Type Codes:

- **TELE_SYNC**: Synchronous teledentistry
- **TELE_ASYNC**: Asynchronous teledentistry
- **MHEALTH_APP**: Mobile health application
- **SMS_MESSAGE**: SMS/text messaging
- **WEARABLE**: Wearable devices
- **MIXED_DIGITAL**: Multiple digital interventions

Outcome Type Codes:

- **PLAQUE**: Plaque index/score
- **GINGIVAL**: Gingival index/bleeding
- **CARIES**: Dental caries measures
- **KNOWLEDGE**: Oral health knowledge

- **BEHAVIOR:** Behavior change measures
- **SATISFACTION:** Patient satisfaction
- **ADHERENCE:** Treatment adherence

Population Codes:

- **PEDIATRIC:** Children (0-17 years)
- **ADULT:** Adults (18-64 years)
- **ELDERLY:** Elderly (65+ years)
- **MIXED:** Mixed age groups

Area codes

- Urban
- Rural
- Other

Effect Size Conversion Reference:

- **SMD:** Standardized Mean Difference (Hedges' g preferred)
- **MD:** Mean Difference
- **OR:** Odds Ratio
- **RR:** Risk Ratio
- **Risk_difference:** Risk Difference

QUALITY CONTROL CHECKLIST

- All mandatory fields completed
- Effect size data internally consistent (CI includes point estimate)
- Sample sizes sum correctly for binary outcomes
- FOR OVERLAPPING:** Primary study lists complete and formatted correctly
- FOR OVERLAPPING:** Factor codes standardized across extractions
- AMSTAR-2 domains completed systematically
- Page references provided for all key data points
- Extraction confidence and notes completed

Special Instructions for Overlap Analysis:

- Items marked **FOR OVERLAPPING** are critical for overlap assessment using CCA/wCCA calculations
- Ensure primary study lists use consistent formatting (FirstAuthor_Year)
- Factor codes must be identical across systematic reviews addressing same intervention-outcome combinations
- Geographic scope helps assess population overlap
- Search end dates enable temporal overlap assessment.